

Hybrid of MoSe₂-Ni(OH)₂ nanosheets as efficient electrode material for high energy asymmetric supercapacitors

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Abstract

Ni(OH)₂ is a promising materials for supercapacitors, but it suffers from capacitance decrease with repeated cycles at high current density. To enhance the specific capacitance and stability performance at high current densities, a newer MoSe₂-Ni(OH)₂ nanohybrid has been prepared by a simple one step hydrothermal synthesis. The maximized synergistic effect among Ni(OH)₂ nanosheets and MoSe₂ resulting in its excellent electrochemical properties. The MoSe₂-Ni(OH)₂ hybrid electrode exhibits a higher specific capacitance of 1175 F g⁻¹ at 1 A g⁻¹ than Ni(OH)₂ nanosheets. In addition, the MoSe₂-Ni(OH)₂ hybrid based asymmetric supercapacitor provides a high energy density of 43 Wh kg⁻¹, power density of 8181 W kg⁻¹ with the capacitance retention of 91.6% even after 5000 cycles at high current density of 5 A g⁻¹. When charged for only 1 min, two asymmetric supercapacitors assembled in series give power to light-emitting-diodes for more than 5 min, indicating the great potential of prepared MoSe₂-Ni(OH)₂ nanohybrid for excellent energy storage.

Keywords: Molybdenum diselenide, Ni(OH)₂ nanosheets, Asymmetric supercapacitor, Cyclic stability